

LOCALISED INKJET PRINTING OF RESIN ADDITIVES FOR SELECTIVE PROPERTY ENHANCEMENT

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Keywords: Composite manufacture, Additive deposition, Inkjet printing, Low-cost, Mechanical testing

ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced polymers in aerospace structures contain a multitude of additives and modifiers within the matrix to increase certain properties. These ancillary materials are added in a bulk manufacturing process such that a uniform concentration is achieved throughout the composite. However, this is neither resourceful of materials nor a cost-efficient process since the additives are not specifically applied in locations where they are most effective. Novel additive deposition technologies, such as liquid resin injection, have shown how the controlled deposition of additives provides the ability to optimise local properties, such as around stress concentrators. In this research, inkjet printing is investigated as a potential method for interlaminar deposition of fillers and additives. Thermoplastic toughening particles are used as an example, but the aim of the research is to develop a method that can be used for the deposition of any resin additive. A comparison was made between the use of a commercial inkjet printer and a customised inkjet printer specifically designed to print onto a composite. Issues associated with the compatibility of inkjet cartridges and modified ‘inks’ resulted in a manual ‘printing’ of the additive to mimic an inkjet printer. Open hole tensile testing and Digital Image Correlation analysis saw a 3.8% increase in strength of specimens containing the toughener compared to a control.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer composite materials are comprised of reinforcing fibres, usually carbon, glass or aramid, which carry loads placed onto the structure and a polymer matrix resin that resists out of plane and impact loading. The desirability of composites is driven by the promise of enhanced structural properties and a reduction in weight, which reduces fuel costs for airliners. Today it is commonplace to see the use of composite materials in primary structures such as the fuselage and wings, and civil airliners can comprise up to 50% weight of composite materials in the construction of the airframe [1]. However, the high manufacturing costs associated with composites limits their success. To further improve performance, resin additives are often included in the formulation of high-performance matrices to tailor the properties of the composite. Also known as modifiers, these ancillary materials have a wide range of functions, some of which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Examples of matrix additives

Resin Additive	Additive Function
Fire retardants [2]	Suppresses combustion of polymer
Release Agents	Facilitates removal of moulding
UV inhibitor/stabiliser	Protects against discoloration/disintegration
Fillers	Reduces cost and prevents exotherm
Conductive	Enables conductivity and electromagnetic shielding
Micro/Nano toughening agents [3]	Increases strength/fracture toughness

Additives can account for up to 20% of the total material by weight [4]. When a batch of resin is manufactured in bulk, any ancillary materials are added by percentage weight to achieve desired properties and a uniform concentration throughout the matrix. However, the addition of ancillary materials, such as resin additives, adds mass to the matrix and to the resulting structure. A lot of the time the use of a resin additive is only required in certain locations, for example the use of a toughening additive where the strain is matrix dominant and the fibre reinforcement carries a reduced load. Therefore, a bulk manufacturing process for composite matrices is neither cost efficient nor optimum for utilisation of resources. By improving the control of additive deposition, manufacturers can tailor the application to local areas that require modification. In turn this will improve the consumption of material, optimise structural performance, reduce material cost and lead to a further reduction in weight of composite structures.

A further drive towards the need for a novel additive deposition process, is the increasing use of dry fibre composites, due to their low cost and high shelf life [5]. Currently there are difficulties with including additives in resin infusion processes, due to the high resin viscosity and particles agglomerating ahead of the reinforcing fibres. As the resin flows through the preform, filler particles become entangled and concentrated in additive rich locations. The matrix effectively has a gradient in concentration across the cured component, which has a detrimental effect on the properties. The use of micro or nano scale particles reduces the effect of filtering, but an evenly distributed concentration cannot be guaranteed. The proof of concept for a novel and cost-effective additive control procedure would be promising for the future of filler incorporation of both pre-impregnated and dry fibre composites.

An example where local matrix reinforcement may be useful is post-cure machining, where holes often must be drilled to enable bolts or rivets to be fitted. Stanier et al. investigated the use of graded or hybrid matrices in FRP's as a mode of increasing the fracture toughness around stress concentrators such as holes [6]. By grading the matrix using a resin injection process, a resin 'patch' was introduced around a hole to create a core shell toughened hybrid epoxy matrix. Open hole tensile testing showed a 15% increase in strength over a single constituent matrix.

Inkjet printing has been a well-established and proven technology since the 1980's [7]. Inkjet printers can be readily bought off the shelf for a relatively low cost, considering the high accuracy and repeatability of the machinery. Expanding on the technology and applying it to the issues previously mentioned there is potential to open new opportunities for additive deposition.

A previous investigation at the University of Bristol [8] into alternative deposition methods of resin additives included the use of a HP 2540 series inkjet printer for printing ink onto glass fibre composite. The main aim of this research is to improve the control of resin additives within composite materials using low cost, commercial scale inkjet printing. A commercial inkjet printer will be customised to accept different resin additives, when formulated into inks, and plies of different fibre material or orientations. Within this preliminary study, deposition of thermoplastic particles will be trialled. However, the wider purpose of this research is to develop a method that can be used for a variety of additives and help improve manufacturing of multifunctional composite materials.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Inkjet Printing Development

One of the main issues highlighted in the previous investigation [8] was the tendency of the particles to clog the printhead and nozzle. This was due to the size of the additive particles being too large and nano/micro scale particles were suggested for future work. Furthermore, it was noted that the printer would jam when an attempt was made to print onto 0° fibres. When paper is inserted into a printer it is fed through a curved track during printing. It is easy to curve and fold paper in all directions, however, composite materials resist bending along the fibre direction. To combat this the

customised inkjet printer used in this work was designed to use a flat feed tray and the substrate size was chosen to avoid the composite plies coming into contact with any moving parts of the customised inkjet printer.

An HP Deskjet 2542 series inkjet printer was disassembled, with all the main components removed from the outer housing. A frame was designed using Autodesk Inventor Pro (2019) to omit any issues associated with using a regular inkjet printer for printing on to pre-impregnated composite material. The main structure holding the print carriage, circuit boards and motors was manufactured from 3 and 10 mm thickness poly(methyl methacrylate) sheets using a laser cutter (Trotec Speedy 400). The structure was bonded together using a 1-part adhesive (RS Components) and a range of nuts, bolts and washers. Steel bearings were also used to facilitate free motion of the feed tray with minimal resistance. The final machine is shown in Figure 1. Single black ink cartridges (HP 301) were used for all printing and the functionality of the customised inkjet printer was initially compared to a regular HP Deskjet 2542 printer with paper used as a substrate.

Figure 1: Final assembly of customised printer

2.2 Ink formulation

The printheads in an inkjet printer are designed to work with a certain viscosity of ink. To ensure that the customised inkjet printer can deposit the additives the ink formulation, containing the additive of choice, must be matched to the viscosity of the original ink. To achieve this a qualitative viscosity experiment, using an inclined plane of glass, was conducted to determine the viscosity of the ink in the printer cartridge, and the volume percentage of additive required to match. The set-up included a 300 × 300 mm pane of glass inclined at 37° supported by steel weights. The time taken for 100 µl drops of fluid to flow from the top of the glass to the bottom were recorded and a mean taken. A variety of particle concentrations were used in the experiment until the viscosity of the ink was matched.

2.3 Manufacture of Test Specimens

The additive chosen in this preliminary work were 0.5 µm polystyrene microspheres (Thermo Scientific) in a 10 weight % latex suspension with water [9]. Specimens containing both no thermoplastic additive (control) and interlaminar thermoplastic microparticles (modified) were manufactured as 16 ply panels using SE 84 carbon fibre pre-preg (Gurit) [10], and a quasi-isotropic lay-up [(+45/-45/0/90)₂]_s.

Once laid up onto tool plates the composite panels were covered with a vacuum bag and then

placed into a temperature-controlled oven for 6 hours at 90 °C (2 °C/min ramp rate from RT to 90 °C) to cure.

2.4 Mechanical Testing and DIC Imaging

To compare the performance of printed and control specimens, open-hole tension (ASTM D5766M [11]) was conducted to calculate failure strength [8]. Mechanical testing was conducted using an Schenck Hydropuls PSA Universal testing machine with a 75 kN load cell and a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. A commercial DIC system (LaVision Strainmaster 5 MP) was used to capture the strain field evolution during deformation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Functionality of customised inkjet printer

The feasibility of the customised inkjet printer when compared to the regular inkjet printer are highlighted using images of printed material. Figure 2 shows the result of a yellow square printed onto carbon fibre pre-preg using a regular HP desktop printer.

Figure 2: Yellow ink printed onto pre-preg using regular HP printer

Initially the customised inkjet printer was used to print regular coloured ink onto a piece of paper to ensure that the print heads were working correctly. The images in Figure 3 show a comparison of a grey 50 × 50 mm square printed onto paper with regular HP printer ink by both the customised inkjet printer and a regular inkjet printer. Note the images are to scale to highlight the distortion seen in the customised inkjet printer.

Figure 3: Comparison of print quality between Left – The regular inkjet printer. Right - The customised inkjet printer. Each printer was programmed to print a 50 × 50 mm square.

3.2 Viscosity Formulation

The results from the viscosity experiment are highlighted in Table 2. The time indicated is for each drop to run 280 mm down the glass pane.

Table 2: Propagation time of each fluid in viscosity trial

Drop	Distilled Water [s]	HP 301 black ink [s]	20% Thermoplastic Suspension [s]	30% Thermoplastic Suspension [s]	40% Thermoplastic Suspension [s]
1	9.42	21.65	24.23	20.83	22.85
2	9.15	21.46	19.92	19.52	22.31
3	9.23	21.48	18.02	21.38	20.83
4	9.30	21.68	16.45	21.43	21.68
5	8.78	20.62	17.30	20.40	21.36
6	-	-	18.68	20.13	22.18
Average	9.18	21.38	19.10	20.62	21.87

From the results obtained, linear interpolation was used to calculate the concentration of thermoplastic particles to give the same viscosity as the ink. The calculation indicated the required volume of thermoplastic suspension to match the viscosity of the printer ink to be approximately 35% mixed with 65% pure distilled water.

3.3 Functionality of Printing Suspension

Initial printing trials using the formulated thermoplastic “ink”, aimed to produce a 50 × 50 mm square onto paper, this was printed as a very faint grey colour. It was noted that there were no streaks, which indicated a good print quality. However, it was not evident whether the printed geometry was in fact the thermoplastic suspension, trace amounts of ink, or a mixture of the two. A second geometry was a 200 mm bar to assess if a larger geometry affected the quality of the print. Similar to the square, the colour was a faint grey with no streaks. However, further printing trials were unsuccessful, with no material being deposited from the cartridge nozzle.

As the thermoplastic suspension clogged the print heads, and it was not possible to deposit the toughener, the thermoplastic suspension was applied through a manual ‘printing’ process. 100 µl of the suspension was applied as a strip of 36 mm in width across the centre of the plies. An inkjet printer provides a very fine even distribution of print material onto the substrate. Manual application would not be able to achieve such a thin layer, therefore resulting in a greater number of particles between each ply than from an inkjet printhead. Instead, a decision was made to apply the additive between every other ply to account for the increased concentration of particles. The ‘printed’ plies as shown in Figure 4 were left to rest for approximately 10 minutes to allow any water to evaporate before they were added to the lay-up.

Figure 4: Carbon fibre ply with 'printed' additive strip. In the centre of the strip the holes for open hole tension testing were drilled. Note – The white areas to the left of the strip of additive are from reflected light.

3.4 Mechanical Testing and DIC

The open-hole tensile testing was successful, with all of specimens failing around the hole as expected. Figure 5 shows an example before and after failure.

Figure 5: Left – Schematic of open hole tension testing specimen, Middle – Specimen before tensile test, Right – Specimen after failure.

A stress-strain curve was plotted for each specimen shown in Figure 6. The control and printed specimens are represented by the red and blue curves respectively. The anomalous result of one of the printed specimens is also shown as a broken blue curve but is omitted from any further calculations. Mean and standard deviations of the failure strengths were calculated and are found in Table 3.

Figure 6: Stress-Strain plots from mechanical testing

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of failure strengths

	Mean Failure Strength [MPa]	Standard Deviation [MPa]
Control Specimen	441	5
Printed Specimen	464	6.75

Using the LaVision DIC software, post-processing output images of the strain field on the surface of the specimens. The images showed the evolution of deformation, but for the case of this research the final image before failure is used for the analysis. Figure 7 shows the strain before failure for a control and printed specimen. The scale bar is a key to indicate the level of strain.

Figure 7: Left - Strain field of control specimen before failure. Middle - Strain field of printed specimen before failure. Right – Strain scale.

4 DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the printed image on to carbon fibre pre-preg with a regular inkjet printer. The quality of the printed geometry supports the hypothesis that inkjet printing is feasible for the deposition of additives onto preforms. First of all, there was a high degree of accuracy in the printed geometry, the resulting print was measured, and all dimensions were to the mm as defined (50×50 mm). The edges of the printed square are also straight, which shows there is no distortion. Another important point is the even distribution of ink provided by inkjet technology. If the technology was successfully applied to resin additive deposition, the control of fillers and modifiers would evidently be of high quality. However, the main downside of using the regular printer is the difficulty in feeding fibres in directions other than 90° .

The customised inkjet printer has also shown both strengths and weaknesses in its design. Due to the complications with the suspension and clogging in the printhead seen in the regular inkjet printer, no attempts were made to print onto composite material using the customised inkjet printer. Instead, its preliminary performance was assessed by printing ink onto paper. The substrate feed tray performed as designed with a smooth operation. After calibration, A 50×50 mm square was printed onto paper, with HP printer inks, using both the customised inkjet printer and a regular inkjet printer to compare the performance. As shown in Figure 3, the customised inkjet printer print was streaky. This is due to the greater distance between the print nozzle and the substrate for the customised inkjet printer. This greater gap was incorporated into the design to allow composite to feed through with the backing paper still attached. Although it was not trialled, it is thought that the distortion will be less severe for printing onto composite because the substrate will be closer to the print nozzle, owing to the greater thickness of composite plies compared to paper. However, further modification of the printer can be conducted to bring the printheads closer to the substrate. Compression of the printed square is seen in

the direction of print for the customised inkjet printer, suggesting that the feed tray travelled at a slower speed than the paper in the regular inkjet printer. Reducing the friction between the feed tray and the customised inkjet printer frame will help to alleviate this.

Ink cartridges commonly use a synthetic foam to control the flow of ink through to the printhead and nozzle. The sponge-like material is an open cell rubber compound, which contains hydrophobic agents to further regulate the flow [12]. It is therefore critical that the viscosity of the additive suspension is such that it can flow similar to ink within the cartridge reservoir. If the suspension is too viscous there is a risk that the particles will agglomerate within the foam. However, a formulation with a lower viscosity will contain a low concentration of particles. Matching the viscosity of the additive suspension to that of ink, ensures a maximum concentration of microspheres without jeopardising the flow through the porous medium. The viscosity of typical printer ink is 2-5 mPas containing approximately 80% water [13]. Although great effort was made to promote a steady flow in the ink cartridge, the deposition of thermoplastic toughener was unsuccessful. Particles were selected by their size such that they have a small enough diameter to move through the cartridge foam, the printhead and nozzle without any hindrance. The rationale behind using micro scale particles was to avoid aggregation in the cartridge ahead of the foam insert. Further efforts were made to match the viscosity of the additive suspension to the viscosity of ink to ensure the feed rate of the additive was sufficient while maintaining a satisfactory concentration of microspheres. A combination of additive particle selection and viscosity formulation was not enough to overcome the issues associated with transferring foreign materials through an inkjet cartridge and print head. Attempts were made to clean the nozzles with acetone and replace the suspension without success. Also, the printing technology used in both the customised inkjet printer and regular inkjet printer use thermal print heads [14]. It is thought the low volumes of suspension in the cartridge combined with an increase in temperature, due to the heating elements, results in rapid crystallization and clogging of the print heads.

The open-hole tensile testing of the specimens proved to be successful. Figure 6 shows that the printed specimens consistently showed a higher strength, the printed and control specimens had an average failure strength of 464 MPa and 446 MPa respectively. This shows that the incorporation of the additive increased the strength of the material by approximately 3.8%. Due to the manual addition of the particles, as it was difficult to achieve an even distribution of particles. However, Table 3 shows that alongside the increased average failure strength of the 'printed' specimens, the standard deviation for both specimens is similar. Although the manufacturing methods didn't provide a consistent quality, it did not show in the variance of the results. For this research, a simple increase in strength is not the aim. More focus is given to the method of manufacture.

Figure 7 shows the strain fields of the specimens right before failure. In the left image of the control specimen, a red 'butterfly' effect can be seen around the hole. A red line indicating high strain is seen for both $\pm 45^\circ$ plies as well as the 90° (horizontal). These lines indicate the mode of failure of the specimen due to the stress concentration of the hole. When compared to the control specimen, the DIC image for the 'printed' specimen has a considerably different strain field. The ply direction under the most strain is the 90° , which can be seen in the image on the right, along with some edge effects around the hole. The dominant red patch in the 90° ply direction indicates a matrix dominant load case, since the fibres take minimal load in the transverse direction. This suggests that the thermoplastic microspheres have toughened the epoxy. Another detail to note on the DIC imaging is the extent at which the high strain (red) moves away from the hole. It is evident that the higher strain regions of the control specimen cover nearly twice the distance from the hole compared to the 'printed'.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Due to issues associated with printing the thermoplastic suspension, the aim of the research has not directly been satisfied. Ideally, the microspheres would have been printed onto the preform using the customised inkjet printer. However, the customised inkjet printer has shown progress in terms of adapting current technology to accept composites as a substrate for printing. Furthermore, the adhesion

of the ink onto pre-preg along with the dimensional accuracy shows promising scope for the future. The manual deposition of the thermoplastic toughening agent showed a 3.8% increase in strength in the open hole tension test specimens, which is expected to increase if manufacturing methods are improved. In addition, DIC imaging proved the ability of the hybrid matrix to absorb energy and constrain the strain to a region around the stress concentrator.

Future work would include combining all that has been learnt to create automated printing of resin additives. Firstly, the customised inkjet printer may need to be adapted and re-calibrated to remove the distortion of the printed patterns. This preliminary study focused on the deposition of thermoplastic, which was ultimately unsuccessful. However, the aim of the research is to apply low cost commercial scale inkjet printing technology to the deposition of additives for composite material manufacture. Therefore, a number of different additives need to be trialled to ascertain if inkjet technology can be used for the deposition of multiple types of resin additives.

To conclude, inkjet printing technology can be adapted to print onto composite preforms. The mechanical testing has shown that a manual particle deposition, representing inkjet printing, was successful. With a cartridge compatible additive suspension, the future of inkjet printing appears feasible. Specifically, the deposition of thermoplastic particles to create toughened hybrid matrices could be a potential use of inkjet printing in industry to enhance and improve the properties of composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council through the EPSRC Future Composites Manufacturing Hub [grant number EP/P006701/1]. Within the University of Bristol, we would like to thank Mr James Filbin and the Hackspace for support with manufacture of the customised inkjet printer.

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